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THE POSSIBILITIES OF VIDEO LAPAROSCOPY IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CLOSED TRAUMA LIVER AND SPLEEN

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ANNOTATION

Summary: During 2011-2021, video laparoscopic surgery was performed in 117 patients aged 18 to 75 years with stable hemodynamics with closed liver and spleen lesions in the Samarkand branch of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences. Of these, 84 (71.8%) are men, and 33 (28.2%) are women. The amount of hemoperitoneum in the abdominal cavity (in cases within 150-200 ml), according to stable hemodynamics and UTT, is treated conservatively. The results of all clinical, laboratory and instrumental studies were analyzed. UTT monitoring repeated verification was carried out every 2 hours. Laparoscopic surgery was performed in patients with a degree of lesion and a volume of hemoperitoneum up to 500 ml, laparotomy-with a volume of hemoperitoneum more than 500 ml. Complications after laparoscopic surgery were observed in 11 (9.4%) cases, mortality - in 5 (4.2%). The duration of stay of patients in the hospital was 24.4 (5-10) days.

Key words: closed abdominal trauma, liver injury, laparoscopy

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ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ВИДЕОЛАПАРОСКОПИИ В ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ЗАКРЫТОЙ ТРАВМЕ ПЕЧЕНИ И СЕЛЕЗЕНКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Актуальность: При закрытых травмами печени и селезенки в течение 2011-2021 гг. в Самаркандском филиале РНЦЭМП была проведена видеолaparоскопическая операция 117 пациентам в возрасте от 18 до 75 лет со стабильной гемодинамикой. Из них 84 (71,8%) составляют мужчины, а 33 (28,2%) - женщины. Количество гемоперитонеума в брюшной полости (в случаях в пределах 150-200 мл), по данным стабильной гемодинамики и УТТ, лечится консервативно. Были проанализированы результаты всех клинических, лабораторных и инструментальных исследований. Мониторинг УТТ повторная проверка проводилась каждые 2 часа. Лапароскопическая операция проводилась у больных при степени поражения и объеме гемоперитонеума до 500 мл, лапаратомия-при объеме гемоперитонеума более 500 мл. Осложнения после лапароскопической операции наблюдались в 11 (9,4%) случаях,

смертность-в 5 (4,2%). Продолжительность пребывания больных в стационаре составила 24,4 (5-10) суток.

Ключевые слова: закрытая травма брюшной полости, травма печени, лапароскопия

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JIGAR VA TALOQNING YOPIQ SHIKASTLANISHLARDA VIDEOLAPAROSKOPIK USULDA TASHXISLASH VA DAVOLASHNING IMKONIYATLARI

ANNOTASIYA

Dolzarbliq: Jigar va taloqning yopiq shikastlanishlari bilan 2011-2021 yillar davomida RSHTYOIM Samarqand filialiga gemodinamikasi stabil bo'lgan 18 yoshdan 75 yoshgacha bo'lgan 117 nafar bemorda videolaparoskopik operatsiya bajarildi. Shulardan 84 (71,8%) nafari erkaklar, va 33 (28,2%) nafarini ayollar tashkil qiladi. Barqaror gemodinamika va UTT ma'lumotiga ko'ra qorin bo'shlig'ida gemoperitoneum miqdori (150-200 ml dan oraliq'da bo'lgan hollarda), konservativ davolanadi. Barcha klinik, laborator va instrumental tekshiruvlar natijalari tahlil qilinib borildi. UTT monitoringi har 2 soat vaqt oraliq'ida qayta tekshiruv olib borildi. Parenxematoz a'zolarining Moor tasnifining OIS (**Organ Injury Scaling**) shkalasi (I-III-darajalari) bo'yicha shikastlanish darajasi va gemoperitoneum miqdori 500 ml gacha bo'lganda bemorlarda laparoskopik amalyot, gemoperitoneum miqdori 500 ml dan oshganda laparotomiya amalyoti amalga oshirildi. Laparoskopik amalyotdan keyingi asoratlar 11(9,4%), o'lim xolatlari 5 (4,2%) holatlarda kuzatildi. Bemorlarning kasalxonada qolish muddati 24,4 (5-10) sutkani tashkil etdi.

Kalit so'zlar: yopiq shikastlanishlar, jigar shikastlanishi, laparoskopiya,

Dolzarbliq. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti ekspertlarining fikriga ko'ra, " Mexanik shikastlanishlar natijasida sodir bo'lgan o'lim to'rtinchi o'rinda turadi va 40 yoshgacha vafot etgan odamlar orasida esa birinchi o'rinda turadi, o'smirlar va voyaga yetganlar orasida 80% tashkil qiladi[1]. Qorin bo'shlig'ining yopiq shikastlanishlarida jigarning shikastlanish darajasi 12,0% dan 46,9% gacha, shok holatidagi qorinning qo'shma shikastlanishlarida esa 49,4% gachani, taloqning shikastlanishi esa 17-30% gacha, qorinning qo'shma shikastlanishlarida esa o'rtacha 40,0% gachani tashkil qiladi [1.3]. So'nggi o'n yilliklarning o'ziga xos xususiyati shikastlanishlar strukturasi o'zgarishi, jarohatlar og'irligining oshishi, asosan qo'shma va ko'p shikastlanishlar ulushining ortishi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ularning darajasi 55,0-80,0% ga etadi. Ushbu toifadagi shikastlanishlarda o'lim ko'rsatgichini yuqoriligi va nogironlik bilan tavsiflanadi, mos ravishda 50,0% va 74,0%. Qorin bo'shlig'i organlarining yopiq shikastlanishlarining ko'payishi ushbu patologiyalarni tashxislash va davolash usullarini optimallashtirishni talab qiladi. Shu munosabat bilan, bu muammo dolzarb va talab bo'lib qolmoqda [2.4]. Qorining yopiq shikastlanish orasida birinchi o'rinni yo'l-transport hodisalari (baxtsiz hodisalar) 60-62%, qolgan qismlarini esa o'rtacha, qastdan shikast yetkazish 24-26 %, balandlikdan yiqilishlar 12-16 %, uy jarohatlari 4-6 % egallaydi [2, 4,15].

Bu holatda eng ko'p shikastlangan organlar: taloq (40-55%), jigar (35-45%) va retroperitoneal soha organlari (15%) tashkil qiladi [5,6]. Jigarning yopiq shikastlanishi bilan o'lim darajasi yuqori bo'lib qolmoqda. AQSh, Yevropa va Yaponiyaning yetakchi klinikalarining ma'lumotiga ko'ra, 31-46% tashkil qilmoqda [7,9,13]. O'limga olib keladigan sabablarning ko'pligi jigar shikastlanishining darajasining og'irligi bilan ham, yopiq shikastkangan bemorlar orasida qo'shma shikastlanishlar bilan birga kelishidir. Jigar shikastlanishini xirurgik davolashning standart usuli bu laparatomiyadir. Shu bilan birga so'nggi yillarda innavasion texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi natijasida ushbu turdagi bemorlarda miniinvaziv diagnostika va davolash usuli videolaparoskopiyadan muvaffaqiyatli foydalanish to'g'risida paydo bo'lgan ko'plab xabarlar mavjud taktikani sinchkovlik bilan ko'rib chiqish zarurligini taqozo etmoqda [9, 10,11].

Maqsad. Jigar va taloqning yopiq shikastlanishlarida videolaparoskopik usulda davolash imkoniyatlarini yaxshilash.

Material va usullar: Jigar va taloqning yopiq shikastlanishlari bilan 2011-2021 yillar davomida RSHTYOIM Samarqand filialiga gemodinamikasi stabil bo'lgan 18 yoshdan 75 yoshgacha bo'lgan 117 nafar bemorda videolaparoskopik operatsiya bajarildi. Shulardan 84 (71,8%) nafari erkaklar, va 33 (28,2%) nafarini ayollar tashkil qiladi. Bemorlarni o'rtacha yoshi 55,5 (18-75) tashkil qiladi. Shikastlanishlarning sabablari quyidagilar: yo'l transport xodisasi – 68 (58,1%) nafar, balandlikdan yiqilish- 24 (20,5%) nafar, kriminal holatlar natijasida – 16 (13,7%) nafar va uy jarohati 9 (7,8%) nafar holatlarda kuzatilgan. Jarohat olgan vaqtdan boshlab to shifoxonaga yetib borgangacha bo'lgan vaqt oralig'i bo'yicha dastlabki 1 soat ichida 59 (50,4%) nafar, 2 soatgacha 37 (31,6%) nafar, 6 soatgacha 6 (5,1%) nafar, 12-24 soat oralig'ida 15(12,8%) nafar shikastlangan bemorlar murojat qilib kelgan. RSHTYOIM Samarqand filialiga 117 nafar bemordan 71 (60,7 %) nafari tez tibbiy yordam mashinasida, 46 (39,3%) nafar bemorlar esa shaxsiy yo'l mashinasida shifoxonaga murojat qilib kelgan.

Shikastlanganlarning 52 (44,4 %) nafarida qorin bo'shlig'ini yopiq shikastlanishi, yopiq kranioserebral shikastlanishlar 30 (25,6 %) nafaarda, ko'krak qafasi shikastlanishlari 15 (12,8 %) nafar, qo'l va oyoqlarning shikastlanishlari 11 (9,4%) nafar, chanoq sohasi a'zolarining shikastlanishi 9 (7,8 %) nafar bemorlarni tashkil qiladi. Shikastlanganlarning umumiy holati bo'yicha 25 (21,4%) holatida og'ir, 92(78,6%) holatida esa o'rtacha og'irlikda deb baholangan.

Natija. Qabul bo'limiga murojat qilgan barcha bemorlar qorin bo'shlig'i UTT o'tkazildi. Tekshiruv natijasida qorin bo'shlig'ida gemoperitoneum miqdori (150-200 ml dan oralig'da bo'lgan hollarda), gemodinamikasi stabil bo'lgan bemorlar shoshilinch xirurgiya bo'limiga yotqizildi. Bu yerda barcha klinik, laborator va instrumental tekshiruvlar natijalari tahlil qilinib borildi. UTT monitoringi har 2 soat vaqt oralig'ida qayta tekshiruv olib borildi. Parenxematoz a'zolarining Moor tasnifining OIS (**Organ Injury Scaling**) shkalasi (I-III-darajalari) bo'yicha shikastlanish darajasi va gemoperitoneum miqdori 500 ml gacha bo'lganda bemorlarda laparoskopik amalyot, gemoperitoneum miqdori 500 ml dan oshganda laparotomiya amalyoti amalga oshirildi.

Gemoperitoneum hajmining oshishi, davom etayotgan qon ketishining klinik va laborator ko'rsatgichlari bilan birga kelishi xirurgik davolash uchun ko'rsatma xisoblanadi. Laparoskopiyani qo'llash uchun ko'rsatmalar Moor tasnifining OIS (**Organ Injury Scaling**) shkalasi bo'yicha organlarni shikastlanishi (I-III-daraja), gemodinamik ko'rsatkichlarning barqarorligi, kovak a'zolar shikastlanishining rentgenologik belgilari yo'qligi, anamnezidan 2 yoki undan ortiq laparatom kesmalar bilan operatsiya o'tkazmagan bo'lsa, diafragmaning yorilishining rentgenologik belgilarining yo'qligi, II va III 3 oylik xomiladorlikni yo'qligi, UTT ma'lumotlariga ko'ra gemoperitoneum hajmi 500 ml dan oshmasligi ko'rsatma hisoblanadi. Tatqiqotimizdagi 117 nafar bemordan organlarning shikastlanishini OIS shkalasi bo'yicha I-II darajali 30 nafarida diagnostik laparaskopiya (konservativ davo) amalyoti olib borildi. Shulardan organlarning shikastlanishini OIS (**Organ Injury Scaling**) shkalasi bo'yicha IV-VI darajali, gemoperitoneum miqdori 500 ml dan ortiq bo'lgan, qorin bo'shlig'i qo'shni a'zolarininig shikastlanishi bo'lgan, jigarining ikkala bo'lagining yorilishi, jigarining 2 ta bo'lagida chegaralangan shikastlanish, bilan birga qorinparda orti sohasi gematomasi va birga taloq yorilishi bilan kelganligi 25 nafar bemorda qaytadan laparatomoya (konversiya) amalyoti amalga oshirildi. Laparotomiya uchun ko'rsatmalar parenximatoz a'zolar yorilganda qorin bo'shlig'iga intensiv qon ketish vaqtida laparoskopik usulda qon ketishini tezda to'xtatishni iloji yo'qligi (OIS shkalasi bo'yicha IV-VI darajalar, jigar segmentlarining 5-7 yorilishi, jigar va taloq yorilishining aktiv qon ketganda), paraduodenal gematomaning mavjudligi, va 62 nafar bemora laparaskopik amalyot amalga oshirildi. (1-jadval).

1-jadval.

Amalyot natijalariga ko'ra taqsimlanishi

Amalyot turlari	Tahlili
Laparoskopik amalyot	62 (53,1%)
Diagnostik laparaskopiya (konservativ davo)	25 (21,3%)
Laparatom amalyot (konversiya)	30 (25,6%)

Laparoskopik amalyotdan keyin 11 (10.9%) nafar bemorada asoratlar kuzatildi. Operatsiyadan

keyingi erta davrda jigar jarohatini OIS shkalasi bo'yicha 1-darajali jarohatini koagulyatsiyasidan keyin takroriy qon ketish 2 (1,98%) nafar bemorda qayd etilgan. Qayta relaparoskopiya yordamida jarohat argonplazmasi koagulyatsiyasi bajarildi va "Taxokomb" qo'llanildi. Bemorlarning 1 (0,99%) holatda jigar osti sohasida absess aniqlanda, bu takroriy jarrohlik yondashuv talab qildi. Bemorlarning 3 (2,97%) nafarida shifoxona ichi pnevmoniyasi kuzatilgan. Bemorlarning 2 (1,98%) nafarida biloma kuzatildi, teri orqali kirish yo'li bilan drenajlanadi, so'ngra sog'aygunga qadar UTT nazorati ostida bo'ladi, Bemorlarning 1 (0,99%) nafarida oshqozon va o'n ikki barmoqli ichakning eroziyasi natijasida oshqozon-ichakdan qon ketish kuzatildi. Bemorlarning 2 (1,98%) nafarida sistit belgilari kuzatilgan (2-jadval).

2-jadval.

Asoratlar ko'rinishi	Bemorlar soni n=62	%
Takroriy qon ketish	2	1.98
Jigar osti sohasi absesi	1	0.99
Pnevmoniya	3	2.97
Biloma	2	1.98
Sistit	2	1.98
Me'da-ichak traktidan qon ketish	1	0.99
Jami	11	10.9

O'lim holati 5 (4,2%) holatda kuzatildidi. Shulardan 2 (1,7%) holatda peritonit rivojlanishi. Yana 2 (1,7%) holatda o'lim sababi norevmatik pnevmoniya natijasida sepsis rivojlanishi. Qolgan 1 (0,8%) holatda o'lim o'tkir yurak-qon tomir etishmovchiligi tufayli sodir bo'lgan.

Laparoskopik amalyotning afzallik tarafi xirurgik yordamning kamroq shikastlanishi bilan bogliq bo'lib, ichki organlarning shikastlanishi deyarli kuzatilmaydi, operatsiya davomiyligi kamayadi, bemorlarni mehnat faoliyati tezroq tiklanadi. Olib borilgan tajriba shuni ko'rsatadiki, gemoperitoneum hajmi va qon ketish intensivligi darajasi har doim ham laparotomiya qilish zarurligini belgilamaydi.

Biz davolash jarayonida laparoskopik usulda davolashni oldingi uch yil davomida qorin bo'shlig'i shikastlanishi bilan og'rigan bemorlarning davolash natijalarini retrospektiv tahlil qildik. Shu bilan birga, qorin bo'shlig'ining yopiq jarohati tufayli operatsiya qilingan shikastlanganlarning 31,6 % bemorlarda jigarning yuzaki yorilishlari, ichak tutqichini yorilishi borligi aniqlandi, bunday bemorlarda laparoskopik usulda operatsiya qilingan. Ushbu tadqiqotda keltirilgan laparotomiya usulidan foydalanish barcha holatlarida, hozirgi kungacha o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan, aniq ko'rsatmalarni hisobga olgan holda, laparotomiya uchun ko'rsatmalar saqlanib qolmoqda.

Laparoskopiya uchun ko'rsatmalarni aniqlashda bir nechta tahlillarga amal qildik:

1) UTT yordamida qorin bo'shlig'ida gemoperitoneum miqdori 500 ml dan ko'p bo'lmagan hollarda:

2) Barqaror gemodinamikaga ega bo'lgan bemorda:

3) Kovak a'zolar shikastlanishining rentgenologik belgilari yo'qligi:

4) Anamnezidan 2 yoki undan ortiq laparatom kesmalar bilan operatsiya o'tkazmagan bo'lsa:

5) Diafragmaning yorilishining rentgenologik belgilarining yo'qligi:

6) Pnevmotoraks belgilarining yo'qligi:

7. II va III uch oylik xomiladorlik yo'qligi:

Xulosa. Olingan tahlillar taqdim etilgan materialda diagnostika xatolari va o'tkazib yuborilgan shikastlanishlar yo'qligini hisobga olgan holda, ushbu turdagi shikastlanishlarda laparoskopiyaning yuqori diagnostik ahamiyatga ega ekanligini aytishimiz mumkin. Jigar shikastlanishlarining og'rligiga qarab shikastlanganlarning laparoskopik davolash natijalarini tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatdiki, jigarning shikastlanishinig Moor tasnifining **OIS** (Organ Injury Scaling) shkalasi bo'yicha organlarning shikastlanishi I-II darajali shikastlanishlarida konservativ davolash mumkin va davom etayotgan qon ketish belgilari mavjud bo'lsa, laparoskopik operatsiya samarali davolash usuli hisoblanadi.

Jigar va taliqning yopiq shikastlanishi bo'lgan bemorlarda laparoskopiyadan foydalanish juda yuqori ma'lumotga ega va gemodinamik ko'rsatkichlarning barqarorligi bilan u laparotomiyaga etarli va xavfsiz alternativ bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin, bu bilan esa behuda laparotomiyalarning oldini olishga, operativ shikastlanishlarni kamaytirishga va ushbu og'ir turdagi bemorlarni davolash natijalarini yaxshilashga imkon beradi.

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